

The Development of COIL and COIL-like Practices Around the World.

世界におけるCOIL実践の発展.

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The COIL network of collaborative learning has been growing steadily for more than ten years, yet COIL is only one system in the broader field of international eLearning. As we move through the innovation stage of COIL development and begin to push for broader adoption it is important to take a wide view of the field, both to understand what has already been attempted and to identify new opportunities for growth and improvement.

Introduction

Technology has always played a vital role in education, from the invention of the abacus, through the first printing presses, to the rise of the computer age, its impact has created significant pedagogical shifts in our approach to the field. During the 1970s Illich (1971) advocated the use of computer networks to create a more fluid system of education existing outside of institutional boundaries. While his ideas were not taken up in the manner he proposed, during the 1980s and 1990s programs of distance learning were developed which began to blur the lines between physical and virtual academic participation (Mason, 1989). In 2004 the State University of New York (SUNY) began a Cross National Project to increase its ability to participate in what was then called Globally Networked Learning, the efforts of multiple universities to develop courses in which students from separate countries would collaborate in the production of coursework. In 2006 SUNY created a new Center for Collaborative Online International Learning (COIL) to focus on these international programs and since then the COIL network has expanded to include a broad coalition of international higher education institutions responsible for a wide variety of courses and numerous developments in the theory of collaborative learning (Moore and Simon, 2015).

The Development of COIL

The benefits of such courses are immense. For many students these courses are their first, or only, opportunity to experience direct international communication and interaction. The virtual exchanges at the heart of the courses can act as an alternative to physical mobility or, preferably, a supplement to it, either by preparing students for future travel or maintaining previously established connections. The interactions

provide opportunities for language skill acquisition and practical use, while also boosting the student's levels of intercultural and global competence. Through this they provide an effective countermeasure to the dangers of racism, xenophobia and intolerance which continue to plague many societies. Finally, they provide a broad platform for engaging student's digital and media literacy, giving them a chance to develop communication skills that have become a vital element of social and business interaction.

COIL courses have, however, expanded upon their language and culture focused beginning. In collaboration with other universities SUNY has now run courses covering such diverse themes as European Politics, Religion and Conflict, the Psychology of Terrorism, Human Rights, and Global Environmental Politics. At the same time online education has also expanded, such that there is now a broader field of general work and research, beyond the COIL network, which also deals with the same issues of collaborative online learning.

COIL-like Programs

The area of Computer Supported Collaborative Learning (CSCL) has also grown in recent years. Unlike COIL programs, these may lack an international component but engage many of the same communicative skillsets and technological platforms (Fulton, 2015). Another mode of study, focusing more specifically on language and cultural exchange is Telecollaboration, with a variety of programs such as Cultura placing an emphasis on communication skills (Chun 2014). More recently, such programs have been rebranded as Online Intercultural Exchange (Dooly and O'Dowd, 2012) and the content has begun to broaden, much like COIL before it (Tcherepashenets, 2015). As a result, the line separating their content from that of COIL programs can often be no more than the terminology used. This issue of systemic identity can be confusing, with both COIL and OIC falling within the scope of what is also known as Virtual Mobility (VM). While Virtual Mobility can also include pure single-institution distance learning, it has been defined by the European Union as "a set of activities supported by information and communications technology, including e-learning, organized at institutional level, that realize or facilitate transnational and/or international, collaborative experiences in a context of teaching and/or learning" (Council of the European Union, 2013).

Working under this banner of Virtual Mobility a broad network of European Universities have engaged in a variety of international collaborative programs in recent years under the aegis of the Open Universities for Virtual Mobility (OUVM) coalition. Some members of this group helped establish the Virtual Mobility Collaborative Laboratory (VMCOLAB) which coordinated the participation of multiple universities in the running of a wide variety of courses, though institutional participation was often consecutive rather than

concurrent, i.e. the collaborative element was more focused on the universities involved rather than the students (Dima, 2015). The group also established the TeaCamp training program to provide structured guidance for educators interested in participating in institutional collaboration (Fuede, 2009). Many of these European initiatives, however, benefitted from Erasmus funding which ran only until 2015. As a result both VMCOLAB and TeaCamp projects have now concluded and it remains to be seen how European VM networks will develop in the future.

The Broader Field

There have also been developments taking place outside purely academic institutions. NPO's such as Europace have been involved in a number of, now completed, projects such as the Real Virtual Erasmus (ReVE) and the Venus series of virtual seminars (Reynolds, 2008). In the US meanwhile, the private firm ePals has created a networking system for secondary level educators and students interested in establishing international linkages. Its intuitive and user-friendly interface might serve as a model for COIL emulation in the future (Demski, 2008). These connections are one of the vital requirements for expanding COIL programs, finding educators and institutions with similar aims and interests to one's own. Yet, as time goes by it is becoming ever easier to find like-minded souls. International conferences and symposia on eLearning and Distance Education are becoming commonplace, with May 2016 seeing SUNY COIL holding their own 10th anniversary conference.

As professional networks expand so too does the literature in the field, with authors producing a wealth of recent works on eLearning (Khan, 2015; Salmon, 2013), Online Collaborative Learning (Kamara, 2014; Cress, 2016), Collaborative Pedagogy (Garrison, 2015) and Online Pedagogy (Harasim, 2011). The number of academic journals related to the field also continues to expand.

Technological advances also increase at a steady pace with new software such as Trello and Slack making collaboration ever-more streamlined and Learning Management System (LMS) providers, such as Blackboard, now tailoring their products specifically for collaborative requirements. Other software solutions have been designed with educator's needs in mind, such as the VLMS system for tracking and evaluating the frequency and depth of student contributions to online discussion forums (Jyothi, 2010). There are dangers inherent in the field's use of technology though, such as programs choosing to focus on systems which are more popular or 'flashy' rather than those which are the most practical for the course's collaborative requirements (Bosch, 2015). There are also questions regarding how technology is best utilized in promoting truly collaborative, rather than cooperative, activity (Chang and Hannafin, 2015) and the difficulty of ensuring that both teachers and students are sufficiently media literate to participate in courses (Koehler, 2013).

Institutional Concerns

Dealing with such problems is, however, far more an issue of institutional support than it is a problem inherent in the technology or the people themselves. Courses live or die with the level of assistance and guidance they receive from their host institutions and the local government. It should be clear that without university support courses cannot hope to succeed, yet, more broadly, the growth and development of COIL, or similar, programs, is significantly affected by the national policy toward eLearning in general or Virtual Mobility specifically. In South Korea the KERIS agency has been established to facilitate global exchange and the promotion of ICT use in education, through activities like the hosting of international e-Learning symposia (Keris, 2015). Yet, while exemplary, long-term support from such agencies is far from sure. In the United Kingdom, BECTA was tasked with a similar government remit to promote ICT in education and achieved many successes and widespread acclaim. Even so, in 2011 the agency was shut down due to budgetary issues, with a significant impact on the country's Educational ICT programs (Arthur, 2010).

In comparison, Japan has yet to establish any dedicated agency focused on ICT in Education, yet it has stated that it hopes to achieve “a wide-ranging network in government-industry-academia collaboration and creation of social momentum for ICT in education”. It has also claimed that it wishes to use ICT as a means of promoting “coexistence and international cooperation among different cultures and civilizations”, and of enabling “children with different backgrounds and various abilities to create new value in collaboration through good communication” (MEXT, 2011).

Conclusion

Whether these aims will see a surge in Japanese institutional support for COIL-like programs remains to be seen. In the meantime the onus remains upon educators to network, coordinate and innovate in their efforts to help the field develop. In his study of technological adoption, Rogers (1962) identified 5 stages: Innovators, Early Adopters, Early Majority, Late Majority, and Laggards. Given that there are over 23,000 universities worldwide and that, at most, one or two hundred of them are engaged in any form of structured collaborative online international programs, it is safe to say that current practitioners are among the innovators. Even among these, the level of penetration of such courses remains low with most universities conducting only a handful of experimental courses rather than ensuring that all students experience some form of experience in virtual mobility. Given this early state, and the inarguable fact that eLearning will only grow in importance in the future, COIL-practitioners are faced with considerable freedom in how they develop their courses. There are many existing examples to use as models but far more room exists to experiment and try new ideas. Only through building new professional networks and

new institutional partnerships can innovations occur and new opportunities arise. In the meantime, any temporary setbacks in establishing such support should be recognized as minor hurdles to be crossed on the path to broader acceptance and usage of COIL-like systems in higher education.

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